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INVERSE ANALYSIS FOR COMPOSITE SINGLE-LAP ADHESIVELY BONDED JOINT

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Outline

Introduction

Interface elasticity

Inversion method for interfacial parameters

Inverse analysis for composite SLJ

Conclusions

Background

Widely applied

- ✓ lower structural weight
- ✓ design flexibility
- ✓ lower fabrication cost

Composite bonded joints

- ❑ Strict process requirements
- ❑ Crack initiation spreads easily
- ❑ Weak bonding detects difficultly

Certification carefully!

INVERSE ANALYSIS FOR COMPOSITE SINGLE-LAP ADHESIVELY BONDED JOINT

Motivation and Key Issues

- Bonded process and service environment may have effects on the mechanical properties of the interface
- Inspect the interfacial properties to analyze the strain distribution accurately

Objective

- Develop analysis approach for interfacial mechanical properties of adhesively bonded joint

Approach

- Interface elasticity theory, finite element method (FEM) and experimental-based inverse method

INVERSE ANALYSIS FOR COMPOSITE SINGLE-LAP ADHESIVELY BONDED JOINT

Interface elasticity

Bulk material

$$\sigma_{ij}^b = C_{ijkl}^b \varepsilon_{kl}^b$$

$$\sigma_{ij,j}^b = 0$$

Interface

$$\sigma_{\alpha\beta}^s = C_{\alpha\beta\gamma\eta}^s \varepsilon_{\gamma\eta}^s + \tau_{\alpha\beta}^0$$

$$[\sigma] \cdot \mathbf{n} = -\nabla_s \cdot \sigma^s$$

- Subscript b denote the bulk material, and s denote the interface;
- $\tau_{\alpha\beta}^0$ is the interface residual stress;
- $[\sigma]$ is the difference between the stress of two adjacent phases near the interface;
- ∇_s is the divergence of interface.

Interfacial finite element formulations

Strain energy

$$U = U^b + U^s$$

$$U^b = \frac{1}{2} \iint_V (\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^b)^T \boldsymbol{\sigma}^b dV = \frac{1}{2} \iint_V \mathbf{a}(\mathbf{B}^b)^T \mathbf{C}^b \mathbf{B}^b \mathbf{a} dV$$

$$U^s = \frac{1}{2} \iint_S (\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^s)^T \boldsymbol{\sigma}^s dS = \frac{1}{2} \iint_S \mathbf{a}(\mathbf{B}^s)^T \mathbf{C}^s \mathbf{B}^s \mathbf{a} dS$$

External work

$$W = \frac{1}{2} \iint_V \mathbf{a}^T \mathbf{N}^T \mathbf{f} dV$$

Interfacial finite element formulations

The boundary conditions on the interface: $[\sigma] \cdot \mathbf{n} = -\nabla_S \cdot \sigma^S$

So, the stresses of different phases do not continue on the interface

strain energy for the element which on the lower side of the interface

$$U = \frac{1}{2} \int_V \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^T \mathbf{C} \boldsymbol{\varepsilon} dV + \frac{1}{2} \int_S \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^T [\boldsymbol{\sigma}] dS = \frac{1}{2} \int_V \mathbf{a}^T \mathbf{B}^T \mathbf{C} \mathbf{B} \mathbf{a} dV + \frac{1}{2} \int_S (\mathbf{B}^S \mathbf{a})^T [\boldsymbol{\sigma}] dS$$

- $[\boldsymbol{\sigma}]$ denote the difference between the stresses of upper side and lower side on the interface

Interfacial finite element formulations

$$\Pi = U^b + U^s - W$$

Principle of minimum potential energy $\frac{\partial \Pi}{\partial \mathbf{a}} = 0$

$$K = \sum_i^V \int_{V_i} \mathbf{G}^T \mathbf{B}^T \mathbf{C} \mathbf{B} \mathbf{G} dV + \sum_i^S \int_{S_i} \mathbf{G}^T (\mathbf{B}^s)^T \mathbf{C}^s \mathbf{B}^s dS$$

$$P = \sum_i^V \int_{V_i} \mathbf{G}^T \mathbf{N}^T \mathbf{f} dV + \sum_i^S \int_{S_i} \mathbf{G}^T (\mathbf{B}^s)^T (\boldsymbol{\sigma}^s + [\boldsymbol{\sigma}]) dS$$

Inversion method for interfacial parameters

Related errors calculated by simulation- experiment correlation model:

$$F(\mathbf{X}) = \sum_{i=1}^N D(\mathbf{X}, i) \quad D(\mathbf{X}, i) = |\varepsilon_{11}^{TEST}(i) - \varepsilon_{11}^{FEM}(\mathbf{X}, i)|$$

- $D(\mathbf{X}, i)$ represent the difference between numerical and experimental result of i th measured point
- \mathbf{X} represent the interface parameter, it can be determined by minimization of $F(\mathbf{X})$

Interfacial strain measured by fiber brag grating (FBG) [Canal et al. Compos. Struct. 112 (2014) 241-247].

Inversion method for interfacial parameters

The process to find the interface parameters, which matched with the experimental results best, could be depress as

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{ll} \textit{Find:} & \mathbf{X} \\ \textit{Minimize:} & F(\mathbf{X}) \\ \textit{Subject to:} & \mathbf{X} \in \mathbf{X}^{\textit{hunt}} \end{array} \right.$$

The genetic algorithm could be used to find the minimum value of $F(\mathbf{X})$

- $\mathbf{X}^{\textit{hunt}}$ is the hunting zone of interface parameters are defined according to the properties of adherends and adhesive.

Solving process by using genetic algorithm

Initialization of interface parameter population

➤ Multiple sets of binary codes

➤ Multiple sets of interface parameters

➤
$$F(X) = \sum_{i=1}^N D(X, i)$$

➤ finding the best X by the selection, crossover and mutation operation on its corresponding binary codes

➤ Defined interfacial mechanical properties

Inverse analysis for composite SLJ

- All the geometric parameters and material properties of composite single-lap adhesively bonded joint used here are the same as given by Canal et al. [Compos. Struct. 112 (2014) 241-247].

Inverse analysis for composite SLJ

mesh details

- 2D plane strain FEM model
- A minimum element size of 0.05 mm
- Can provide appropriate accuracy for interfacial strain prediction
- $\mathbf{X}=\mathbf{X}(C_{1111}^S, C_{1212}^S, \tau_{11}^0)$

Inverse analysis for composite SLJ

	Modulus (GPa)				Poisson's ratio		Ref.
	E_{11}	$E_{22}=E_{33}$	$G_{12}=G_{13}$	G_{23}	$\nu_{12}=\nu_{13}$	ν_{23}	
CFRP	126	7.98	3.14	2.85	0.29	0.40	Compos. Struct. 112 (2014) 241- 247
Adhesive	2				0.35		

Interface parameter	C_{1111}^S (N/mm)	C_{1212}^S (N/mm)	τ_{11}^0 (N/mm)
Hunting zone	0~126000	0~6280	-100~100

Inverse analysis for composite SLJ

Related errors $F(\mathbf{X})$ during the solving process

Inverse analysis for composite SLJ

Interface parameter	Optimal solution
C_{1111}^S (N/mm)	1648
C_{1212}^S (N/mm)	3427
τ_{11}^0 (N/mm)	25.5

Conclusions

- An inverse approach is proposed to determine the interface parameters for composite bonded single-lap adhesively bonded joint.
- By utilizing the interface elasticity theory, it is possible to describe the interfacial strain distribution well and character the mechanics properties of an adhesively bonded interface.

Path Forward

Future Work:

- Develop and validate controlled procedure to the cure process, including cure pressure, time and temperature.
- Improve failure analysis model considering interfacial energy.

Benefit to Aerospace Industry:

- Better understanding of interface mechanical properties for composite adhesively bonded joints.
- Assisting in the development of inspect for composite adhesively bonded joints.

Questions and comments are
strongly encouraged

Thank you !